

Simulation and analysis of wind energy potential for turbine systems in Pekanbaru-Indonesia based on MATLAB Simulink

Nicholas Pranata, Fahmy Rinanda Saputri

Department of Engineering Physics, Faculty of Engineering and Informatics, Universitas Multimedia Nusantara, Tangerang, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

The widespread use of electricity today, which is primarily generated from fossil fuels, results in significant environmental consequences due to excessive consumption. Renewable energy has been proposed as a solution to mitigate this issue. In Indonesia, particularly in Pekanbaru City, the demand for electricity currently exceeds the supply. However, this region has substantial potential for renewable energy sources. This study presents the modeling and analysis of wind energy, specifically wind turbine systems, using MATLAB Simulink. The methodology involves identifying existing problems, collecting technical data relevant to Pekanbaru and turbine components, and designing the turbine system within MATLAB Simulink. The results of this system indicate a mechanical power output of 1,191 watts, along with a calculated torque of 48.63 Nm. These findings suggest that the system is suitable for small-scale electricity needs. Further research and considerations are necessary to optimize the design and application of turbine systems for sustainable energy production. By improving the efficiency and scalability of wind energy systems, Indonesia can better address its energy deficit while reducing the environmental impacts associated with fossil fuel consumption.

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Corresponding Author:

Fahmy Rinanda Saputri

Department of Engineering Physics, Faculty of Engineering and Informatics

Universitas Multimedia Nusantara

Scientia Boulevard St., Curug Sangereng, Kelapa Dua, Tangerang, Banten 15810, Indonesia

Email: fahmy.rinanda@umn.ac.id

1. INTRODUCTION

Human life requires energy, whether in the form of food [1], electricity, or other sources of energy. This is essential to sustain life and contribute to human well-being. Today's most widely used type of energy is electricity to power various activities. Energy consumption has been continuously increasing since the rapid development of technology, evident across various sectors such as industrial, commercial, household, and transportation. According to the Indonesian Central Statistics Agency report, there has been an increase in energy consumption [2]. This is also applicable to electricity, as reported by the International Energy Agency (IEA) [3]. The dominant sources of this energy are fossil fuels such as gas, oil, and coal, primarily due to their lower cost compared to other sources.

Nevertheless, the environmental impact of using these fuels has become a global issue, contributing to problems like global warming, climate change, and pollution [4], [5]. This is exacerbated by the fact that the availability of these fuels is significantly diminishing [6]. According to the Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources (ESDM), especially in Indonesia, the availability of crude oil is projected to last for 9 years, gas for 22 years, and coal for 65 years [7]. Hence, continued reliance on these fossil fuels is unsustainable for future generations, necessitating alternative solutions such as the use of renewable

energy [8]. Renewable energy includes solar, wind, hydro, and biomass [9], [10]. These sources are cleaner and can mitigate the impact of global issues resulting from fossil fuel use [11]-[13]. Aside from supplying electricity, renewable energy also helps in job deployment, technology development, as well as minimizing environmental problems [11], [14], [15]. However, several setbacks include unpredictability of the sources, mainly for solar and wind energy, low efficiency, and high initial costs [11], [15]-[17]. Thus, planning for renewable energy must be done to counter this limitation in which may utilize simulation in the early phase. Simulation is a method to replicate physical performance based on systems, processes, and laws using parameters [18]. This method will help in supporting renewable energy development by avoiding unnecessary cost, time, and quality loss using the results analysis. Several software have been used in the case of this source, such as PVSyst, RETScreen, HOMER, and PSCAD.

One of the popular software that is used is called MATLAB or Matrix Laboratory, which facilitates a tool called Simulink to help in creating energy models that will be used as a simulation basis for analysis purposes. Previously, there have been numerous applications based on Simulink in various renewable energy systems. According to a study, a solar tracking system was developed, operating automatically to locate the most optimal light position [19]. To control this system, PID control is employed, consisting of a motor and a solar panel [19]. In another study with geothermal power plants, Simulink was also utilized for simulation by involving two subsystems, P1 and another subsystem for components (VSD and Pump). The results showed that the system's performance was satisfactory, with normal simulation times and responses that did not exhibit significant overshoot [20].

Location selection is also necessary in the early phase of development. In Indonesia, the potential for renewable energy is substantial [21], [22]. Particularly in the Riau province, renewable energy potential is reported as 5950 MW [23]. Table 1 shows the renewable energy potential in Riau, Indonesia.

Therefore, opportunities still exist to create renewable energy-based power generation systems in this area. In contrast with the potential of renewable energy, this region still faces electricity-related problems. Pekanbaru City, serving as the capital of this province, is one of the areas frequently experiencing electricity deficits, making the installation of power generation systems crucial for supplementing the supply [8]. Also, recently, there was a total blackout in the whole city that lasted for hours due to a transmission problem from the State Electricity Company (PLN) in another part of Sumatra Island. This shows how vulnerable the electricity system is if only dependent on this source. For this reason, renewable energy must be implemented as a solution to these issues. Wind energy, along with solar energy, is one of the sources that is mostly available in all parts of the world [24]. Knowing that the potential of this energy has not been implemented, an initial assessment of the wind speed in this area can be made. Using the data from BPS, the wind speed data can be shown in Table 2 [25].

Table 1. The renewable energy potential in Riau [23]

Energy type	Potency	Installed capacity (MW)	Utilization
Geothermal	20 MW	0 MW	0.00%
Water	961,84 MW	114,27 MW	12.00%
Bioenergy-biofuels	7.797.981 TON	3,336,302 MW	42.78%
Bioenergy-biomass	3844 MW	700 TON	18.21%
Bioenergy-biogas	325 MW	33,45 MW	10.29%
Sun	753-1700 MW (4.80 kWh/m ² /day)	1,28 MW	0.02%
Wind	5 MW (3-6 m/s)	0 MW	0.00%
Sea	241 MW	0 MW	0.00%
Total	5.950 MW	848,90 MW	14.27%

Table 2. Pekanbaru wind speed from 2020-2022 [25]

Monthly	Wind speed (m/s)								
	Minimum			Average			Maximum		
	2020	2021	2022	2020	2021	2022	2020	2021	2022
January	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.52	6.00	7.00	9.77	15.00	20.00
February	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.50	6.00	6.00	10.29	25.00	26.00
March	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.40	6.00	6.00	12.86	27.00	28.00
April	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.06	7.00	6.00	9.26	30.00	20.00
May	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.47	6.00	6.00	10.29	21.00	30.00
June	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.60	6.00	6.00	10.29	22.00	20.00
July	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.79	7.00	6.00	10.29	24.00	22.00
August	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.87	7.00	6.00	10.80	27.00	17.00
September	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.80	7.00	6.00	12.86	26.00	24.00
October	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.15	6.00	6.00	8.75	20.00	35.00
November	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.26	6.00	6.00	9.26	27.00	24.00
December	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.47	6.00	6.00	7.72	27.00	26.00

Based on Table 2, the wind speed shows the value of 6-7 m/s average in 2022, which the threshold for small wind turbine implementation lies between 4-4.5 m/s [26], [27]. In correlation with Simulink implementation, several studies regarding wind energy have been reviewed. Two studies show similar context for different regions, namely Cilacap and Tegal [28], [29]. Both discuss the data collection, creation of the turbine model, as well as simulation using parameters such as wind speed, blade radius, air density, tilt angle, and rotor angular speed, which results in 0.2 kW and 0.7 kW, respectively. Even further, another study integrated a generator in the models based on Finite Element Method Magnetics simulation data [30]. Hence, this shows that Simulink serves well features that can facilitate the modeling of wind energy models for research purposes.

In accordance, this research aims to conduct a simulation for the design of a wind turbine system using Simulink-based simulation, specifically in Pekanbaru, Riau, Indonesia. The objective is to provide insights into the potential of wind power generation within the turbine system, focusing on the predetermined location of Pekanbaru. What sets it apart from previous related studies is the choice of a renewable energy source, specifically wind energy, using MATLAB Simulink in this region, which has never been studied. The system's development will then concentrate on designing a turbine system. This study is anticipated to offer a clear understanding of the wind power generation potential in the turbine system, particularly in the specified location. Secondly, the report aims to serve as a reference for further research in comprehending and advancing the integration of artificial intelligence in the context of wind power generation.

2. METHOD

The method applied in this project involves a series of steps to address contemporary issues related to sustainability, particularly in the context of energy. First, the identification of the current issues associated with energy sustainability is done. The next step involves collecting information and data through a literature review, encompassing journals, reports, and other relevant sources.

Subsequently, the selection of the research location becomes a crucial stage, and Pekanbaru is chosen as a suitable research location, given its electricity deficit issues. Information is gathered regarding the technical data on the wind energy potential in Pekanbaru to support the system design. The information is as follows:

- Wind turbine reference model = AWI-E1000T with a radius of 2 meters.
- Wind speed = 7 m/s (maximum) based on Table 2. In 2021 and 2022, the data trend in the average section has a maximum wind speed of 7 m/s.
- $C_p = 0.39$ (maybe obtained theoretically and through simulations).
- $\lambda = 7$ (maybe obtained theoretically and through simulations, based on report reference).
- $\omega = 24.5$ rad/s (obtained through $\lambda = \frac{\omega R}{v}$).
- $\beta = 0$ degrees wind turbine (based on the consideration of maximum C_p).

The next step is to design a wind power generation system for the turbine system. After creating the initial design, artificial intelligence is used, specifically Simulink, to execute and analyze the design. In this step, model validations are made by inputting parameters from previous studies to results with similar output. The process and analysis of the results obtained are crucial steps in evaluating the system's performance. In conclusion, the analysis offers a thorough evaluation of the potential and performance of the proposed wind power generation system. This approach presents a structured method for exploring and solving energy challenges in Pekanbaru, with an emphasis on sustainable solutions.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Wind turbine design

The design of the wind turbine will require the help of other website-based data for the value of the velocity of the wind as well as the turbine specification. The equation used for designing the wind turbine is as (1) [31].

$$P_m = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^2 v^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta) \quad (1)$$

In (1), P_m is the mechanical power output (W), R is the blade radius (m), and v is the wind speed (m/s). Then, C_p is the power coefficient indicating conversion efficiency, λ is the tip speed ratio between blade tip speed and wind speed. The variable of β is the pitch angle, which controls the blade's orientation to regulate power output. In this case, the component of Simulink is integrated based on the above equation. Subsystems are required to satisfy the equation of several variables such as λ and C_p as (2).

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega R}{v} \quad (2)$$

In (2) satisfies the ratio of wind turbine blade tip velocity to the wind velocity. Whilst λ is also affected by the variable β which will eventually form the C_p equation, given as (3) [24], [31].

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_i} = \frac{1}{\lambda + 0.08\beta} - \frac{0.035}{1 + \beta^3} \tag{3}$$

With (3), a subsystem is made. Based on Figure 1, several blocks in Simulink are used as a means of representing the variable. In this case, $1/(u[1] + 0.08*u[2]) - 0.035/(1+u[2]^3)$ is the equation used in which $u[1]$ as λ (lambda) and $u[2]$ as β (beta). Finally, the C_p equation is formulated (according to the approximation method by [32]-[35]) as shown in (4) [24].

$$C_p = 0.5176 \left(\frac{116}{\lambda_i} - 0.4\beta - 5 \right) e^{-\left(\frac{21}{\lambda_i}\right)} + 0.0068\lambda \tag{4}$$

This will require the use of a similar procedure with the prior using blocks that represent the above equation, turning into $0.5176*(116u[1] - 0.4*u[2]-5)*\exp(-21*u[1])+0.0068*u[3]$ in which $u[1]$ acts as $1/\lambda_i$ (the result of the previous block), $u[2]$ as β , and $u[3]$ as λ .

The remaining variables in (1), represented as u^2 and u^3 , will be implemented as blocks in Simulink. Specifically, u^2 will compute the square of the radius, while u^3 will calculate the cube of the wind velocity. These outputs will then be multiplied using a gain block set to the value of pi. The complete system layout is illustrated in Figure 2. Finally, these systems can be converted into subsystems, resulting in a simpler visualization of the wind turbine. These can be shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1. Subsystem for C_p equation

Figure 2. Detailed breakdown of the wind turbine system

3.2. Research analysis

Based on the wind turbine design results generated using MATLAB Simulink, as illustrated in Figure 4, an analysis can be conducted. Using the technical data and (1), the system calculates the mechanical power output of the wind turbine to be 1,191 watts. Additionally, the torque can be determined using (5) [24].

$$P = T\omega \tag{5}$$

Here, P denotes power in watts (W), T represents torque in newton-meters (Nm), and ω stands for angular velocity in radians per second (rad/s). In this case, the calculated torque is 48.63 Nm. These results show that for blades with a radius of 2m, wind speed of 7 m/s, C_p of 0.4513, λ of 7 (recommended for 6-12 m/s incoming wind) [36] and 0 degrees on the β AWI-E1000T wind turbine (with 1,000 W power specification) assumption, the turbine produces power close to 1,000 watts. The selection of 0 degrees for Beta is based on previous similar research that shows that for maximum C_p , Beta should be in 0 degrees [31], [37], [38]. In addition, the C_p obtained through this simulation shows the correlation to the Beta graph, in which for the value 0 degrees and lambda 7, the C_p should be around 0.45, as shown in Figure 4 [39].

Overall, the simulation result is categorized as a small output based on the recommendation in [29], voltage can be generated by wind power generation systems with wind speeds of 2.5 m/s while in this case, the maximum is 7 m/s from the data of Pekanbaru wind velocity) in which this result can be recommended for small-scale electricity needs [29]. This is also supported by the finding that the power coefficient is small (efficiency), and the wind direction in this land area is not too high. Finally, it is also necessary to consider other factors such as geography, proximity to residents, environmental, and noise impacts.

Figure 3. Simplified wind turbine system

Figure 4. Typical $C_p(\beta, \lambda)$ variation graph [39]

4. CONCLUSION

This research presents the simulation results of a specific wind power generation system, particularly focusing on the turbine system, using the equation $P_m = \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi R^2 v^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta)$. Considering technical data, the outcome indicates a mechanical power of 1,191 watts and a torque of 48.63 Nm. This suggests suitability for small-scale electricity needs. For future research, it is recommended to consider factors such as updated wind speed data in Pekanbaru and enhancing the Simulink system by incorporating additional components like generators and batteries, along with their efficiency, including transmission. Furthermore, conducting a comprehensive economic analysis by evaluating different turbine types, product ranges, investment costs, and the resulting benefits could provide deeper insights into the feasibility and optimization of wind power systems. Additionally, integrating environmental impact assessments and exploring hybrid systems combining wind with other renewable energy sources could further enhance the sustainability and effectiveness of renewable energy solutions.

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Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Nicholas Pranata		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	
Fahmy Rinanda Saputri	✓									✓		✓	✓	✓

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support this study's findings are openly provided by the Indonesian Government Bureau called Badan Pusat Statistik, accessed from its website at <https://riau.bps.go.id/id/statistics-table/2/MTQxIzI=/kecepatan-angin.html>.

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BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Nicholas Pranata is a bachelor's student in Engineering Physics at Universitas Multimedia Nusantara. He has extensive experience in research related to renewable energy, energy simulation, sustainability, environment, building science, and control systems using Arduino. Additionally, he has conducted several studies on the impact of engineering education. He has published various articles on these topics and is currently involved in research on several projects, including solar and wind energy, motor control for electric vehicles, and lighting systems for buildings, as well as Arduino control systems. He can be contacted at email: nicholas.pranata@student.umn.ac.id.

Fahmy Rinanda Saputri reached her bachelor's and master's degrees in Engineering Physics from Universitas Gadjah Mada in Indonesia. She is currently an academic in Engineering Physics at Universitas Multimedia Nusantara, Indonesia. Her research interests encompass instrumentation, energy, sensors, and systems, as well as building and environmental simulations. She can be contacted at email: fahmy.rinanda@umn.ac.id.